

Corrigenda

Corrigendum: Differentiation in the ultrastructure of pectiniform antennae in species groups of the genus *Ctenoceratoda* Varga, 1992 (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae). Contributions to Entomology 73(1): 95–107. <https://doi.org/10.3897/contrib.entomol.73.e104072>

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Academic editor: Thomas Schmitt | Received 11 November 2023 | Accepted 15 November 2023 | Published 8 December 2023

In the publication Varga et al. “Differentiation in the ultrastructure of pectiniform antennae” in Contributions to Entomology 73 (1) 2023, 95–107 | DOI 10.3897/contrib.entomol.73.e104072 due to a technical error, the

Figure 14 was dropped out and the Figure 15 was reproduced two times. Therefore, we replace now the correct Figure 14 with the original explanation.

Figure 14. **A.** *C. mallopyga dyschroa* Varga, Gyulai, G. Ronkay and L. Ronkay, 2017, medial part of the antenna with short, asymmetric processes and with long sensilla chaetica in terminal position, with straight or terminally curved sensilla trichoidea, 60× magnification; **B.** *C. mallopyga dyschroa* Varga, Gyulai, G. Ronkay et L. Ronkay, 2017, stalk and dorsal processes of the antenna, with long, nearly straight sensilla chaetica in terminal position, and with straight or terminally curved sensilla trichoidea, 150× magnification; **C.** *C. mallopyga dyschroa* Varga, Gyulai, G. Ronkay et L. Ronkay, 2017, stalk and ventral processes of the antenna, with long, nearly straight sensilla chaetica in terminal position, and with straight or terminally curved sensilla trichoidea, 150× magnification; **D.** *C. mallopyga dyschroa* Varga, Gyulai, G. Ronkay et L. Ronkay, 2017, distal part of the dorsal processes with long, nearly straight sensilla chaetica in terminal position, and with nearly straight or terminally curved sensilla trichoidea, 300× magnification; **E.** *C. mallopyga dyschroa* Varga, Gyulai, G. Ronkay et L. Ronkay, 2017, short ventral processes of the antenna with straight sensilla chaetica in terminal position and terminally curved sensilla trichoidea, 300× magnification; **F.** *C. mallopyga dyschroa* Varga, Gyulai, G. Ronkay et L. Ronkay, 2017, part of the stalk with relatively short sensilla trichoidea, densely covered by narrow, acute sensilla coeloconica, 1000× magnification.